

INVESTIGATING THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF I β CRYSTALLINE CELLULOSE AND DISLOCATED CELLULOSE BY MOLECULAR DYNAMICS SIMULATION

Ali khodayari^{1,*}, Aart W. Van Vuure¹, and David Seveno¹

¹ Department of Materials Engineering, KU Leuven, Leuven, Belgium

* Corresponding author (ali.khodayari@kuleuven.be)

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ABSTRACT

Cellulose, being the most abundant natural polymer on earth, has been widely investigated in several theoretical and experimental studies. The highly ordered configuration of cellulose is mostly responsible for its excellent mechanical properties. Recent developments in computer simulations have encouraged scientists to look for the mechanisms controlling the mechanical behaviour of cellulosic polymers. Modelling the molecular arrangement of the different constituents in the plant cell wall, such as the crystalline and the disordered regions, and hence their contributions to mechanical and hygrothermal behaviour of natural fibres are challenging especially because experimental characterization at the nanoscale is still unclear.

In this work, we have studied the mechanical properties of 36-chain I β crystalline cellulose by Molecular Dynamics Simulations using GLYCAM06 force field. The geometrical arrangement of the crystal model is evaluated and compared with the experimental data. Moreover, a model of cellulose nano-fibrils (CNF) including dislocations is proposed. The elastic properties of the latter model are also investigated. Results of this study can be further used to scale-up the existing models to more general and realistic simulations of CNFs containing both crystalline and disordered regions.

1 INTRODUCTION

Demand for natural and sustainable materials with long life cycle, and possibly made of renewable resources is increasing, due to the fact that growth of the population has led to huge concerns about environment and human health endangered by CO₂ emission coming from industrial development, production and processing [1]. Natural materials, in particular natural fibres have then recently gained the attention of scientists and engineers [2,3] as they can potentially be proper replacement for synthetic materials, such as glass fibres, and can intrinsically decrease health-related risks. Attempts to combine them with polymers, providing enhanced thermo-mechanical properties have been made [4]. Moreover, the extraordinary properties of these materials such as Young's modulus and specific strength have encouraged more and more researchers to put an effort into exploring the usage of natural materials in different industry sectors as in sports industry [5], automobile and transportation industry [6], paper and packaging industry [7,8], and even in biomedicine engineering applications [9]. Nevertheless, still, there have been unclear answers regarding the nano-scale behaviour of natural fibers, mechanically, thermally, effect of moisture, etc.

Cellulose is the most abundant biopolymer known as it constitutes almost half of the plant cell wall. The strength and other mechanical properties of plant fibres are mostly controlled by the amount and arrangement of crystalline cellulose within the cell wall. As an example, Yan et al. [10] showed that flax fibers containing roughly 70% crystalline cellulose show better physical and tensile properties than other natural fibers. However, there are still debates on reasons behind particular behaviours like the non-linear tensile stress-strain curve of natural elementary fibers [11,12]. Additionally, the structure of cellulose crystals has been studied through X-ray scattering [13-15] or diffraction [16] methods but the role of the micro-fibrillar angle on the strength of materials under tensile load remains obscure. Moreover, the contribution of dislocated regions in the plant cell wall to the mechanical properties of natural fibers cannot be ignored [17]. As shown by experiments [18], these regions alongside the amorphous parts such as hemicellulose or lignin, resist less to ambient humidity, leading

to swelling fibers and loss of mechanical properties. Attempts on modifying the wetting and swelling of elementary fibres have been already performed and can be a guideline for further investigations [19].

Recently, Molecular Dynamic (MD) simulations were used to illustrate these aspects of natural materials [20-22]. Amongst all, numerous studies [3, 23] have investigated the mechanical properties of crystalline cellulose, tensile behaviour particularly. Whilst experimental values of the elastic modulus for crystalline cellulose have been reported to fall in between 110 and 220 GPa using various methods of measurement. Paavilainen et al. [20] computed the elastic modulus of a 36-chain nanofibril of 10 nm in length to be 157 GPa. Wu et al [24] in another work, computed the same property for different strain rates. They obtained elastic moduli of 107.8-112.9 GPa using ReaxFF force field. Other simulations were performed by Hao et al. [25] using COMPASS force field on an infinite model for crystalline cellulose, and reported a value of 142 GPa. The same force field was used by Eichhorn and Davies [26] to calculate the Young's modulus of different cellulose crystal phases I α , I β , and II, where the resulting Young's modulus for I β crystal was 149 GPa. On the other hand, exploiting COMPASS force field, Tanaka and Iwata [27] resulted in values ranging from 124 to 155 GPa. In the same manner, other values have been reported widely in several works, e.g. 156 GPa [28], 150 GPa [29]. Nevertheless, there are various factors affecting the calculation of the properties e.g. differences in force field parameters, finite and infinite models. It is worth noting that, typically two models have been used in MD to model crystalline cellulose; an infinite crystal, where periodic boundary conditions (PBC) are used to model the configuration, and a finite model, where a finite nano-fibril is modelled. The former eliminates the inhomogeneity of the surface chains, when solvated in solvent. In other words, structural differences between the interior chains and the exterior ones, in solvated state, will be avoided. The latter model on the contrary, exhibits slight differences in the orientation of hydroxymethyl groups, in presence of solvent. Moreover, twist of the fibril can be modelled when no PBC are implemented. Additionally, accurate cross-sectional area computation in MD has always been a challenge, drastically affecting the final calculated elastic properties. Moreover, Wohler et al. [30] provided an in-depth analysis on the parameters affecting the deformation mechanisms of crystalline cellulose, and investigated the impact of entropy on the stiffness of cellulose nanocrystals. They showed that the effects of entropy can lead to a decrease in elastic modulus when temperature rises.

In this work, we investigated the mechanical properties, namely, elastic properties in longitudinal direction of cellulose I β nanofibril as a characterization criterion for the crystalline and non-crystalline models. Furthermore, we provide an in-depth view of the dihedral angles within the two mentioned models. As any change in some dihedral angles can lead to distortion of the crystal state, one can use these parameters to define the crystallinity of cellulose models. Notably, introduction of the non-crystalline cellulose to crystal regions can be quite crucial in defining the mechanical properties of the fibers at the nano-scale. We expect that the results of this study can pave the way to better modelling and understanding of natural fibers, shedding a light on more complex cellulosic systems.

2 METHODS AND MODELS

All simulations are carried out using GRONingen Machine for Chemical Simulations (GROMACS) 5.1.2 version [31]. GLYCAM06 force field [32], suited for carbohydrates, is used to perform energy calculations. The bonded interactions including stretching and angle potentials are modelled with a quadratic polynomial. Torsional potentials are treated with a three-term Fourier expansion series. Non-bonded terms include van der Waals interactions modelled by a 6-12th power Lennard-Jones potential, and electrostatic interactions with a Coulombic potential. The parameter set is taken from Amber 2018 simulation package [33], and the coordinate and topology files are converted to GROMACS readable files through Acypye python script [34]. TIP3P water molecule is used as the solvent.

2.1 Crystalline cellulose

A 6 \times 6 crystalline cellulose is first modelled in Materials Studio [35]. The crystal lattice parameters and coordinates for the I β crystalline cellulose structure are taken from the crystallographic data reported by Nishiyama et al. [36]. The structure includes 36 chains of cellulose, each being 10 glucose units in length (see Fig.1). The final length of the crystal (L_0) is 5.27 nm having an average cross-section of 3.16 \times 3.29 nm² after the production run. The length of the fibril is calculated considering the

average distance between two ends of the fibril; centre-of-mass (COM) of the O1 from the non-reducing end and centre-of-mass of the O4 from the reducing end. To calculate the cross-sectional area the distance between the COM of the side chains, namely, a and b in Fig.1, are taken as primary values, and multiplied by a correction factor, as the true areal size is slightly larger than $a*b$.

Figure 1. a) Lateral view, and b) cross-sectional view of the crystal model. The yellow highlighted regions are the exterior chains, and the rest are the interior ones.

2.2 Dislocated cellulose

To model dislocations, the equilibrated model of the previous step is taken and undergone a tempering cycle at 700 K to disrupt the crystallinity of the model. Hence, the dislocated model contains the same degree of polymerization, yet, different properties. According to the literature, the hydroxymethyl group is mostly ordered in a trans-gauche (tg) conformation, therefore, having a ω ranging from 158° to 170° degrees. Accordingly, the conformational preferences for the dihedral angles φ and ψ is 262° to 272° and 213° to 221° , respectively [36]. A dislocated cellulose must show different conformations for these angles, as well as the hydrogen bonds, since the planar stacking is basically held together by the intra- and inter-chain hydrogen bonds; namely O3-H3...O5 and O2-H2...O6, flanking the glycosidic linkage, and O6-H6...O3/O2 of the neighbouring chains holding the chains together in each hydrogen bonding plane [37].

Figure 2. Schematic configuration of a cellulose chain. The dihedral angles can be expressed as $\omega = \text{O5-C5-C6-O6}$, $\varphi = \text{O5-C1-O4-C4}$, and $\psi = \text{C1-O4-C4-C5}$

2.3 Molecular Dynamics Simulations

The generated structure is solvated in TIP3P water, centered in a box of $13.7 \times 14.4 \times 15.1$ nm³, and energy minimized using the steepest descent minimization algorithm with an energy minimization tolerance of 10.0 kJ/mol/nm. The minimization step is followed by NVT dynamics of 1 ns, NPT of 1 ns, and a production run of 2 ns.

A leap-frog algorithm is implemented for integrating the Newton's equations of motion [38], with time steps of 2 fs. Bonded hydrogens are constrained with a LINear Constraint Solver (LINCS) algorithm. Verlet scheme is used for neighbour searching, with a cut-off for short-range electrostatics and van der Waals interactions of 1.2 nm. Particle-Mesh Ewald (PMF) is applied to treat the electrostatics in the system. Temperatures are maintained at 300 K, using a velocity rescaling thermostat [39], and extended-ensemble pressure coupling is performed by a Parrinello-Rahman barostat [40], maintaining the atmospheric pressure.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Crystal model

After relaxing the model, a right hand twist is observed (Fig.3) [41,42]. The radial distribution function for the crystal model shows two peaks at 0.146 nm and 0.154 nm corresponding to the C-O and C-C bonds, respectively (see Fig.4). The glycosidic angle C4-O4-C1 has been also measured for the interior chains, as well as the exterior ones, showing 117° and 119°. Noteworthy, the exterior chains show a slight increase in the glycosidic angle as they had to stretch to compensate the twist of the fibril, maintaining the crystal lattice parameters. Conformational angles have been also studied previously [43], and are computed for the crystal model (Fig.5). Distributions of the interior and exterior chains show similar values to the experimental data for φ and ψ , being 270° and 219°, respectively. However, as expected, surface of the crystal shows different behaviour with respect to the inside of it. The interior chains obviously show a Gaussian distribution of a tg conformation at 170°, being 81% of the results falling in between $170^\circ \pm 17^\circ$ for the interior chains. Nevertheless, the surface of the fibril is perturbed by the presence of water, leading to tg alongside some gg and gt conformational orientations.

Figure 3. a) Lateral view, and b) cross-sectional view of the twisted crystal model.

Figure 4. a) Radial distribution functions of the internal (solid blue) and external (dashed orange) residues of the crystal structure, and b) glycosidic angle in the internal (solid blue) and external (dashed orange) chains showing a 2° difference between the two regions.

Figure 5. The conformational dihedrals of the interior (solid blue) and exterior (dashed orange) chains for a) ϕ , b) ψ , and c) ω of the crystal model.

Elastic modulus of the crystal model is computed by applying a harmonic force to the two ends of the structure, providing a strain rate of 0.17 ns^{-1} . One can compute the Young's modulus dividing the stresses by the applied strain (see Fig.6), according to Hooke's law. Computed elastic modulus for the first 5% of strain in this case was $E = 131 \text{ GPa}$ with a confidence level of 98%, also obtained by experimental studies [3].

Figure 6. Stress-strain curve of the crystalline cellulose model.

Figure 7. The conformational dihedrals of the interior (solid blue) and exterior (dashed orange) chains for a) ϕ , b) ψ , and c) ω of the dislocated cellulose.

3.2 Dislocated cellulose

The existence, location, and configuration of the dislocated regions in the plant cell wall, specifically the arrangement of these sections with respect to the crystal regions is controversial [44]. Yet, it is most commonly accepted that the non-crystalline regions are located at the surface and along the main axis of the fibril [1]. Nevertheless, one can argue that, considering the growth and synthesis of the chains from cellulose synthase complex (CSC), and the continuity of these chains to forming crystals, the hypothesis behind existence of amorphous regions can already be rejected. However, to our knowledge, recent studies confirm the fact that the so called amorphous regions consist of mostly dislocated regions, where only the crystallinity is disrupted, leading to a shift in the direction of the

chains. It can also be argued that there is no defect, such as voids, within these regions, otherwise, the mechanical properties of the nano-fibrils could be dominated by the mechanical properties of the defected regions, assuming a series connection of dislocated regions and the crystal ones. Whilst the tensile properties of a flax elementary fibres is measured to be up to values around $E = 75$ GPa [45]; this value can be significantly higher than a model where defects exist, or in other words, the number of connecting chains is lower [20].

To our knowledge, there is no experimental measurements of the dihedral angles within the dislocated regions. To model such dislocations, as mentioned before, the crystal model is tempered for 1 ns at 700 K, 1 ns at 770 K, energy minimized and quenched down to 300 K for 1.5 ns to disrupt its crystallinity. This procedure slightly widens the distributions of φ and ψ , both for the exterior and the interior chains. However, most importantly, the ω values completely cover all the tg, gg, and gt conformations both on the surface and inside the fibril (Fig.7). Notably, in this case, only 15% of the ω results fall in the range of $170^\circ \pm 17^\circ$ for the interior chains, showing the degree of the conformational disorder. This can possibly lead to a decrease in the intra- and inter-chain hydrogen bonds resulting to a decline of the elastic properties (Fig.8).

Figure 8. Stress-strain curve of the dislocated cellulose model.

The elastic modulus for the dislocated cellulose is measured to be 82.7 GPa. From Fig.8 it can be noted that, whilst the fit is up to a great confidence level (98%) correlated with the results, yet the stress-strain slope is slightly increasing at high strains. This non-linear trend can be interpreted as re-crystallization of the fibril, reconstructing some of the hydrogen bonds.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we proposed a model for the dislocated regions in CNFs. Investigating the combination of dislocated and crystalline regions in one model is the starting point of a potential answer to the non-linear stress-strain curve of natural fibres.

We modelled a 6×6 crystalline cellulose using GLYCAM06 force field, and exploited a tempering and quenching cycle to generate a dislocated model. The differences between the dihedral conformational angles were investigated, and we showed that the dislocated model is mostly different in the ω preferential orientation. The disruption of the conformational angles is a possible reason behind weakening the interactions within the chains and hydrogen-bonded planes, provided by the hydrogen bonds, leading to lower mechanical properties. The elastic properties of dislocations were calculated to be 37% lower than that of the crystalline cellulose. Whilst, the original computed value for Young's modulus was 131 GPa, lying on the lower range of the experimentally proposed values for cellulose I β crystals. As mentioned, this drop in the elastic properties can be related to the decrease in the number and/or the energy of the intra- and inter-chain interactions.

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